

“Back to Where It All Started”: Quality of Life of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

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Abstract

Quality of life (QOL) is an essential measure in assessing the reintegration of recovering drug dependents into society. While vital, limited research explores how these individuals manage reintegration challenges, particularly in terms of functionality, environment, social affiliations, and personal growth. Existing studies fall short in capturing the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of recovering dependents after rehabilitation, especially within community settings. This study sought to explore the QOL of community-reintegrated recovering drug dependents, focusing on their characteristics, challenges, coping strategies, and insights throughout their post-rehabilitation journey. Employing a descriptive-phenomenological design, in-depth interviews were conducted with six participants who met inclusion criteria, and their narratives were analyzed using Colaizzi’s method, with validation from both participants and experts in qualitative and addiction research. Fourteen themes surfaced, reflecting their experiences. Findings revealed characteristics such as social restraint, emotional overwhelm, physical health consciousness, and growth orientation. Participants faced notable challenges, including social and structural adjustments, financial burdens, and the sacrifice of personal interests. To cope, they adopted healthy lifestyles, relied on social and spiritual support, and practiced relapse prevention strategies. Additionally, they shared meaningful insights, highlighting the importance of self-improvement, gaining new perspectives, and drawing lessons from past experiences. These findings carry significant implications for developing community support systems and post-rehabilitation programs aimed at fostering holistic recovery, reducing stigma, and enabling smoother reintegration into society.

Keywords: *Quality of Life, community-reintegrated, recovering drug dependents, descriptive phenomenology.*

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Introduction

Navigating the transition from rehabilitation to sober living presents a formidable challenge for recovering drug dependents, who must balance recovery tools learned in treatment with the demands of daily life. Beyond abstinence, successful reintegration requires improvements in quality of life (QOL), including physical and mental health, social functioning, and personal development (Laudet, 2020; WHO, 2022). However, existing literature highlights persistent gaps: individuals often face stigma, financial strain, lack of aftercare, and weak community support systems that leave them vulnerable to relapse (Neale, 2015; Wong, 2018). In the Philippines, where aftercare programs remain fragmented and poorly sustained, these challenges are particularly pressing (Jacobs, 2021).

Previous studies have documented systemic issues in Drug Treatment and Rehabilitation Centers (DTRCs), such as rigid admission processes, insufficient follow-up, and under-resourced services, which undermine recovery outcomes (Manuel, 2017). While some programs, like Sagop Kinabuhi 2 in Davao, aim to address socioeconomic reintegration, they have been criticized for neglecting the lived experiences

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and psychosocial needs of recovering individuals (Gascon, 2021; Munro, 2017). These gaps reveal a limited understanding of how reintegration affects QOL and underscore the need for more person-centered approaches that go beyond economic support to include social belonging, self-growth, and healing spaces within communities.

This study responds to these gaps by exploring the quality of life of community-reintegrated recovering drug dependents, focusing on their characteristics, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights. Guided by the Being, Belonging, and Becoming framework, it offers a multidimensional perspective on reintegration and highlights how community-based initiatives can foster resilience, reduce stigma, and promote sustainable recovery.

Materials and Methods

This study employed a descriptive phenomenological research design to explore the quality of life (QOL) of community-reintegrated recovering drug dependents. Grounded in Edmund Husserl’s phenomenology, the design aimed to capture the essential features of participants’ lived experiences without interpretation. Bracketing was applied to set aside biases and preconceptions, allowing participants’ experiences to emerge authentically. The study was conducted in Davao City, Southern Mindanao, Philippines, which hosts several rehabilitation facilities. Despite efforts to recruit from both public and private centers, participants were recruited exclusively from public rehabilitation centers due to non-disclosure policies and limited referrals from private institutions. Data were gathered from six participants who had completed inpatient rehabilitation at least six months prior and were actively reintegrated into their communities. Participants provided medical clearances and discharge papers, which were kept confidential. Purposive and snowball sampling were applied to select participants with relevant experiences, and each participant identified a key informant, such as a family member or close friend, to validate and triangulate reported experiences. Ethical approval was secured from the SPC-REC, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. A semi-structured interview guide with 12 main questions and 40 probing questions was developed and validated by field experts. Interviews, which lasted 45 minutes, addressed QOL dimensions of Being (health and functioning), Belonging (social integration), and Becoming (personal growth). Each interview included time for orientation, data collection, and debriefing, was audio-recorded with consent, transcribed, and anonymized using pseudonyms. Mental fitness for participation was assessed by a psychologist, and a guidance counselor was available for debriefing. Confidentiality was strictly maintained following the Data Privacy Act of 2012, with all data securely stored for five years. Participants were reimbursed for their time, and findings were presented back to them for verification following Colaizzi’s method. Ethical guidelines from the APA (2017) were observed throughout, emphasizing non-maleficence, beneficence, and respect for participants’ rights and dignity.

Findings

The study thoroughly gathered and analyzed data guided by four main objectives: understanding the characteristics, identifying the struggles, exploring the coping mechanisms, and uncovering the insights of community-reintegrated recovering drug dependents.

The Demographic Profile of Participants

The researcher reached saturated data from a total of 6 participants who satisfied the inclusion criteria for this study. The following details concerning these participants are relevant:

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Participants

Pseudonym	Sex	Age	Type of Rehabilitation Center
Richie	Male	39	Public
Leo	Male	29	Public

Eve	Female	41	Public
Hans	Female	36	Public
Dodong	Female	34	Public
Belle	Female	39	Public

The Characteristics of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

Figure 1 presents the themes based on the characteristics of recovering drug dependents following their community reintegration. The researcher identified four emerging themes from the gathered data: Socially Restrained, Emotionally Overwhelmed, Physically Health-Conscious and Growth-Oriented.

Figure 1. The Characteristics of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

Theme 1: Socially Restrained

Recovering drug dependents often experience social restraint during reintegration, feeling limited by both external factors, such as the pandemic, and by internal restrictions within their families or communities. Many report feelings of confinement and surveillance, similar to the structured routines in jail or rehabilitation, where their actions are constantly monitored. These restrictions hinder their ability to form authentic connections and lead to emotional strain. The pandemic further intensified these experiences, as quarantine protocols, health risks, and limited social interactions compounded their sense of isolation.

Theme 2: Emotionally Overwhelmed

Reintegration is also marked by emotional turbulence. Recovering drug dependents frequently struggle with anger management, heightened sensitivity, and conflicts in relationships. Intense emotions such as frustration, stress, and disappointment often lead to impulsive behaviors. Alongside this, many report experiencing emotional isolation, characterized by loneliness and depression, as they lack trusted individuals to confide in. This emotional burden makes it difficult to cope effectively, leaving them vulnerable to setbacks.

Theme 3: Physically Health-Conscious

Despite these challenges, many adopt a health-conscious lifestyle, incorporating practices such as regular exercise, mindful eating, and consistent sleep routines. These behaviors serve as coping strategies, promoting both physical and mental well-being. The development of healthier habits reflects a commitment to recovery and a conscious effort to sustain long-term wellness.

Theme 4: Growth-Oriented

A growth-oriented mindset also emerges strongly among recovering drug dependents. Many focus on self-improvement, embracing positivity, and taking proactive steps toward rebuilding their lives. This includes pursuing new skills, maintaining meaningful work, and fostering independence. Additionally, spiritual reconnection and leaving past struggles behind contribute to resilience and personal transformation, allowing them to move forward with renewed purpose.

The Challenges of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

Figure 2 presents the themes based on the various challenges faced during community reintegration by recovering drug dependents. The researcher identified three emerging themes from the gathered data: Transitioning to Community Reintegration, Sacrificing Personal Interests, and Dealing with Financial Strain.

Figure 2. The Challenges of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

Theme 5: Transitioning to Community Reintegration

Recovering drug dependents often faced overwhelming responsibilities as they transitioned back into society. The stability and structure of rehabilitation were replaced with unstructured routines, long work hours, and irregular sleep, which made it difficult to maintain balance and well-being. Many reported struggling with self-discipline and direction as they adjusted to new demands.

Theme 6: Sacrificing Personal Interests

Another major challenge identified was the need to sacrifice personal interests and hobbies to prioritize work and financial responsibilities. While this shift was necessary for survival and stability, it often led to feelings of frustration and loss, as individuals placed their own aspirations aside for family and livelihood.

Theme 7: Dealing with Financial Strain

Financial struggles emerged as one of the most pressing challenges. Recovering drug dependents often faced unstable employment, long working hours, and the constant pressure of meeting daily expenses. This strain not only threatened their physical health but also added psychological stress, making sustained recovery more difficult.

The Coping Mechanisms of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

Figure 3 presents the themes based on the different coping strategies employed by recovering drug dependents facing challenges during their community reintegration. The researcher identified four emerging themes from the gathered data: Healthy Lifestyle, Social Support, Strong Spiritual Beliefs, and Relapse Prevention.

Figure 3. The Coping Mechanisms of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

Theme 8: Healthy Lifestyle

Adopting a healthy lifestyle emerged as a vital coping mechanism for recovering drug dependents reintegrating into society. Nutrition and dietary choices were central, with many becoming more conscious of reducing unhealthy food and prioritizing fruits, vegetables, and balanced meals to improve health and prevent illness. Physical activity such as sports, exercise, and group activities like Zumba provided both physical benefits and opportunities for social interaction, helping to instill discipline and a sense of achievement. Equally important was the recognition of rest and recovery as essential to well-being, as individuals balanced work demands with the need to restore energy and maintain emotional stability. Collectively, these practices highlight how healthier routines strengthen resilience and stability during reintegration.

Theme 9: Social Support

Strong support systems played a crucial role in sustaining recovery. Family support offered stability, encouragement, and financial or emotional assistance, serving as a foundation for resilience. Positive relationships with colleagues and in the workplace fostered acceptance, belonging, and motivation, reducing feelings of isolation. Friendships and community connections also provided encouragement, practical support, and guidance in avoiding relapse triggers. Together, these forms of social support created a buffer against challenges, reinforced self-esteem, and strengthened commitment to recovery.

Theme 10: Strong Spiritual Beliefs

Spirituality and faith were consistently identified as core coping mechanisms. Prayer, regular church attendance, and personal faith practices gave recovering individuals a sense of hope, comfort, and guidance. These practices reinforced their resilience, provided meaning in moments of struggle, and fostered a sense of belonging within faith communities. For many, spirituality also served as a resource

in dealing with financial, relational, and emotional challenges, reinforcing the belief that recovery is sustained not only through personal effort but also through divine guidance.

Theme 11: Relapse Prevention

Participants described relapse prevention as an intentional and ongoing process. Selective social connections—distancing from peers who may trigger relapse and choosing healthier relationships—were crucial. Boundary setting, including the ability to say “no” to risky situations, empowered individuals to protect themselves from potential setbacks. Self-empowerment further strengthened recovery, as individuals took pride in resisting temptations and celebrated small victories, reinforcing confidence in their ability to sustain sobriety. These strategies highlight the proactive efforts of recovering drug dependents in maintaining long-term recovery.

The Insights of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

Figure 4 presents the themes based on the different insights learned by recovering drug dependents all throughout their community-reintegration journey and post-rehabilitation life. The researcher identified three emerging themes from the gathered data: Realizing Intentional Efforts to Better Oneself, Gaining New Perspective, and Acquiring Wisdom from the Experiences.

Figure 4. The Insights of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

Theme 12: Realizing Intentional Efforts to Better Oneself

Recovering drug dependents recognized that sustained recovery requires intentional efforts to improve oneself. By embracing mindfulness in their choices and actions, they found a clearer sense of direction and purpose in life, often motivated by their families and the responsibilities they hold. This intentionality fosters both growth and resilience, allowing them to face challenges with greater stability and accountability.

Theme 13: Gaining New Perspective

Recovery also brought about a transformative shift in mindset, allowing individuals to reevaluate their past and look forward with hope and gratitude. This new perspective was marked by a greater appreciation for family, healthier relationships, and lessons that reshaped how they viewed themselves and the world.

Theme 14: Acquiring Wisdom from the Experiences

Past struggles with substance use became powerful sources of wisdom, enabling recovering dependents to better understand the consequences of their choices and embrace new beginnings with clarity. This wisdom grounded them in gratitude, resilience, and a renewed sense of life's possibilities.

Discussion

This section discusses the research findings, highlighting data that directly answer the research objectives and the themes collectively identified throughout the analysis. The researcher utilized the Centre for Health Promotion model to comprehensively describe the quality of life, specifically the characteristics, struggles, coping mechanisms, and insights, of recovering drug dependents living their post-rehabilitation journey during community reintegration.

Recovering drug dependents, by definition, are individuals who have previously struggled with substance use and are actively engaged in the process of recovery. This journey often involves overcoming significant challenges and is influenced by various personal and social factors (Rozinei, 2022). Many report negative life events, such as health issues or legal troubles, as catalysts for seeking help (Brunelle, 2015). However, studies show that support systems, including family, peers, and recovery groups, are essential for successful recovery. Drug dependents in recovery often benefit from structured environments and social-based recovery groups, which provide emotional support and accountability (Viveiros, 2022).

Characteristics of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

The reintegration of recovering drug dependents into the community is a multifaceted journey marked by various challenges and personal transformations. Four major themes emerged from the findings, encapsulating the characteristics of the participants as they journey their recovery: Socially Restrained, Emotionally Overwhelmed, Physically Health-Conscious, and Growth-Oriented.

Social inhibition was a dominant characteristic among the recovering drug dependents, reflecting the difficulties they encountered in rebuilding their social lives. Many described feelings of unease and hesitancy in engaging with others, rooted in the stigma associated with their history of substance use. This challenge was further compounded by external factors, such as the pandemic, which limited opportunities for social interaction and reinforced isolation. In the study of Kuri (2015), participants report a sense of exclusion and isolation from their communities, exacerbating their struggles with reintegration. Social exclusion has been linked to increased relapse tendencies, with negative coping styles mediating this relationship (Chen & Tan, 2023). However, according to Morani (2017), hypervigilance of family members can help recovering individuals stay accountable, reducing the likelihood of relapse. Addressing the broader social and systemic barriers that hinder reintegration is essential. Interventions aimed at reducing stigma and fostering community acceptance can play a crucial role in encouraging social engagement and reintegration.

Another key characteristic was emotional dysregulation, highlighting the participants' struggles with managing their emotions effectively. Indicating a direct relationship between substance use and emotional management challenges, this characteristic is developed because high levels of substance use severity correlate with increased difficulties in controlling impulsive behaviors (Garke, 2021). Psychologically, recovering individuals struggle with emotional clarity, impulse control, and goal-directed behavior, which are critical for effective emotion management (Byllesby et al., 2023). Socially, post-rehabilitation environments may lack supportive structures, making it challenging for individuals to practice new emotional regulation skills (Garland et al., 2018). In effect, many recovering drug dependents reported experiencing intense emotional swings, including anger, frustration, and feelings of isolation, which often strained interpersonal relationships and impeded their ability to adapt to the demands of daily life. Emotional dysregulation leads to strained relationships, as recovering individuals may struggle to communicate effectively or maintain social connections (Abol et al., 2019). Emotional regulation is a

cornerstone of successful recovery, and providing access to counseling services, therapeutic interventions, and skills training in emotional management can help recovering drug dependents handle stressors and triggers, ultimately promoting emotional stability and resilience.

Recovering drug dependents also displayed a shift toward physical health consciousness. Many expressed a commitment to engaging in regular physical activities, such as exercise and sports, as a means of improving their physical fitness and overall well-being. Engaging in physical activities reduces stress, manages emotions, and stabilizes mood, which are crucial for individuals recovering from substance use disorders (Wayoi et al., 2024). This proactive approach to health was often accompanied by other positive habits, including mindful eating and maintaining consistent sleep routines. Furthermore, improved physical health fosters recovery capital by alleviating negative feelings such as boredom and social isolation, thus enhancing social connections and overall life satisfaction (Osborne & Kelly, 2023). These practices not only helped participants manage stress but also contributed to rebuilding self-esteem and fostering a sense of accomplishment. The systematic review indicates that physical activity interventions during substance use disorder treatment can lead to positive outcomes, including a cessation or reduction in substance use, improved aerobic capacity, and decreased depressive symptoms (Florence, 2023).

Despite these challenges, recovering drug dependents demonstrated a strong growth-oriented mindset. Participants in recovery programs often articulate a renewed vision for their lives, emphasizing the importance of setting goals and values for their future (Guabong et al., 2015). This determination to improve themselves and create a better future was evident in their active pursuit of self-improvement through education, skill-building, and cultivating positive relationships. Their focus on personal growth was often fueled by a desire to rebuild their lives and find renewed purpose. Personal growth initiatives, such as setting goals and pursuing new knowledge, significantly contribute to their self-efficacy and motivation to remain abstinent (Niles et al., 2022).

These characteristics provide valuable explanations into the experiences and needs of recovering drug dependents during reintegration. While social inhibition and emotional dysregulation highlight the emotional and social challenges they face, their physical health consciousness and growth-oriented mindset reflect their resilience and capacity for transformation.

Challenges of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

The challenges faced by recovering drug dependents during their reintegration into the community are multifaceted, reflecting the complexities of transitioning back into society. The findings revealed three major themes that describe the challenges of the participants as they progress through their recovery journey: Transitioning to Community Reintegration, Sacrificing Personal Interests, and Dealing with Financial Strain.

One significant challenge involves the process of transitioning itself. Participants described the weight of new responsibilities as overwhelming, particularly after the structured environment of rehabilitation. Individuals face new expectations that can feel insurmountable after the structured environment of rehabilitation (Ingimarsdóttir et al., 2023). The absence of a clear framework in post-rehabilitation life often left individuals struggling to maintain a stable and positive routine. Many report a lack of guidance and support during this critical period, leading to difficulties in navigating adult services (Medforth & Huntingdon, 2018). Furthermore, the lack of social acceptance added another layer of difficulty, as rebuilding relationships and finding a supportive community proved to be a daunting task. A study highlights that lack of social support contributes to relapse among rehabilitated drug addicts. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the necessity for comprehensive support systems, including emotional, practical assistance, and concrete support groups, to aid their reintegration into society effectively (Noor, 2017).

Another challenge revolves around the sacrifices made by recovering drug dependents as they re-enter society. In many cases, they found it necessary to prioritize responsibilities and commitments over personal desires and hobbies. In a study conducted by Szczygiel (2020), Recovering individuals frequently focus on job commitments and family obligations, which can overshadow personal interests and hobbies.

Additionally, many face challenges in reclaiming their identities, often feeling disconnected from their previous selves and interests due to the demands of recovery (Kuri et al., 2017). While these sacrifices were often crucial for fostering stability and accountability, they also resulted in feelings of loss and frustration. The inability to engage in activities that once brought joy and fulfillment created an emotional void, highlighting the importance of finding a balance between personal interests and societal expectations during recovery. The shift in focus can result in a sense of mourning for lost opportunities and personal fulfillment, leading to frustration and emotional distress (Madole, 2022).

Financial strain further compounded the difficulties of reintegration. Participants reported immense pressure to rebuild their lives, which included securing stable employment and managing living expenses. While research has shown that financial stability is crucial for recovery, as it alleviates stress, enhances treatment adherence, and fosters resilience, ultimately facilitating reintegration and personal growth, economic strain on the other hand significantly contributes to poor mental health outcomes, limiting social support and increasing feelings of isolation (Zafar, 2024). After a period of rehabilitation, many faced significant financial burdens, leading to heightened stress and difficulty focusing on recovery and personal growth. This can be detrimental to people in recovery because the lack of adequate resources can lead to increased recidivism and hinder successful reintegration (Barroso, 2024).

Together, these challenges paint a complex picture of the reintegration journey. Transitioning into community life, sacrificing personal interests, and dealing with financial strain reflect the emotional, social, and economic hurdles that recovering drug dependents must overcome.

Coping Mechanisms of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

The journey of community reintegration for recovering drug dependents is marked by their reliance on various coping mechanisms to face challenges and maintain their progress. Four key themes emerged from the findings, highlighting the coping mechanisms utilized by these individuals in their recovery journey: Healthy Lifestyle, Social Support, Strong Spiritual Beliefs, and Relapse Prevention.

A prominent coping strategy is the adoption of a healthy lifestyle, which significantly enhances their overall well-being and resilience. Participants emphasized the importance of prioritizing nutrition, engaging in regular physical activity, and ensuring adequate rest. These practices not only help them manage stress but also improve their physical health and foster a sense of stability in their daily lives. A study indicates that a healthy lifestyle intervention positively impacts recovering drug dependents by promoting better physical health, enhancing psychological well-being, and supporting sustained recovery, ultimately leading to improved treatment outcomes and reduced relapse rates in this population (Kelly, 2021). By embracing a healthier way of living, they create a solid foundation for sustaining their recovery. Research indicates that wellness encompasses connection, awareness, and congruence, which are vital for maintaining recovery from mental health challenges (Cummings & Bentley, 2018)

Social support emerged as another vital coping mechanism, highlighting the critical role of relationships in fostering resilience and providing stability. According to a study, social support significantly enhances motivation, resilience, and success in substance addiction recovery. Emotional, instrumental, and informational support from family, friends, and community fosters stability, helping individuals cope with recovery challenges and preventing relapse, thus improving their quality of life (Rokiyah, 2024). Recovering individuals relied heavily on the encouragement and trust of their families, which served as an anchor during challenging times. Families often provide high levels of emotional support, which is essential for the psychological well-being of recovering individuals (Ghazalli & Ramly, 2023). In addition, strong connections with friends and colleagues created a sense of belonging, offering both motivation and emotional well-being. These positive social networks acted as a safety net, empowering them to rebuild their lives with confidence. Research has it that individuals with larger and more diverse social networks report better treatment outcomes, highlighting the importance of social capital in recovery (Schweitzer et al., 2023).

For many recovering drug dependents, spirituality provided profound solace and strength. Interventions focusing on spirituality have led to increased self-awareness, self-confidence, and a commitment to

positive actions among adolescents recovering from addiction (Ismail et al., 2022). Their strong spiritual beliefs acted as a cornerstone of hope and resilience. One study revealed that spiritual beliefs provide individuals with a framework for understanding and enduring hardships, as evidenced in Christian communities where faith acts as a source of hope (Odia, 2023). Regular practices such as prayer and church attendance deepened their connection to their faith and nurtured a sense of community. Higher spiritual well-being is linked to reduced substance use frequency among recovering individuals (Kane et al., 2023). This spiritual grounding offered them a source of comfort, helping them navigate the uncertainties and emotional challenges of reintegration with renewed determination and inner peace.

Another critical coping mechanism was relapse prevention, which involved deliberate strategies to maintain progress and avoid setbacks. Techniques such as cognitive reframing, acceptance behavior, and self-care practices have been shown to significantly reduce psychological distress and support recovery efforts (Priya et al., 2024). Participants highlighted the importance of selective social connections, actively choosing relationships that supported their recovery. Strong ties with peers who have higher recovery scores correlate with improved recovery outcomes. Conversely, individuals with lower recovery scores often form strong ties with similarly struggling peers, which can hinder their recovery (Jason et al., 2024). They also practiced boundary setting to protect their mental and emotional well-being. A study highlighted that drug cue and craving indicators significantly influence drug use and relapse outcomes. Practicing refusal to triggers can help recovering drug dependents manage cravings, thereby reducing the likelihood of relapse, as supported by the study's findings (Vafaie, 2022). By cultivating self-empowerment, they developed the confidence and skills necessary to sustain a drug-free lifestyle.

Collectively, these coping mechanisms—adopting a healthy lifestyle, fostering social support, maintaining strong spiritual beliefs, and focusing on relapse prevention—demonstrate the multifaceted strategies that recovering drug dependents employ to navigate their reintegration journey. These approaches not only help them overcome challenges but also lay the groundwork for a more resilient and fulfilling life.

Insights of Community-Reintegrated Recovering Drug Dependents

The insights shared by community-reintegrated recovering drug dependents highlight the profound transformations they experienced in their journey toward sustained recovery. There are three main themes that reflect the insights gained by the participants during their recovery journey: Realizing Intentional Efforts to Better Oneself, Gaining New Perspective, and Acquiring Wisdom from the Experiences.

A significant realization among recovering drug dependents was the importance of intentional efforts to better themselves. This insight emphasizes the need for mindfulness in making life choices and the application of learned life skills. A study indicated that self-compassion mediates the relationship between mindfulness and readiness to change, suggesting that cultivating mindfulness can enhance an individual's motivation to improve their life choices (Naderi et al., 2024). By approaching their recovery journey with purpose and clarity, they actively foster personal growth and resilience, equipping themselves to face challenges with determination and focus. Recovery often leads to a renewed sense of self, where individuals reshape their identities beyond addiction (Jean-Berluce, 2024).

Another key insight is the value of gaining new perspectives, which has proven to be transformative for many recovering drug dependents. Participants in recovery reported seeing their circumstances in a new light, which helped them redefine their goals and aspirations (Martinelli et al., 2023). Through their recovery experiences, they reevaluated past choices and gained a clearer understanding of what truly matters. Individuals in recovery frequently reflect on their past decisions, recognizing the impact of their experiences on their current lives (Viergever et al., 2019). This introspection can lead to a desire for change, as seen in those recovering from addiction who view their past struggles as catalysts for personal growth (Tarigan, 2022). This shift in outlook allowed them to envision a more hopeful and fulfilling future, recognizing the significance of support systems and healthy relationships. Such a perspective not only motivates them to stay on their path to recovery but also deepens their appreciation for the positive changes in their lives.

Additionally, the wisdom they acquired from their past experiences became a cornerstone of their recovery journey. People in recovery often reflect on their past, leading to a deeper understanding of their behaviors and motivations (Guabong et al., 2015). This reflective process can foster a sense of responsibility and a commitment to change, as seen in the narratives of those recovering from polydrug dependence (Császár et al., 2024). This hard-earned wisdom offered clarity and purpose, enabling them to embrace new beginnings with a deeper understanding of the consequences of drug use. By acknowledging the importance of healthier choices and relationships, they cultivated a renewed sense of contentment and optimism. Additionally, they can cultivate positive emotions and relationships through peer support, promoting optimism and contentment. The Flourishing Partner model emphasizes leveraging positive relationships and interventions to foster engagement, meaning, and personal growth, ultimately supporting a transformation into flourishing lives (Biondi, 2018). This fresh outlook on life empowered them to appreciate their growth and resilience, finding strength in each step they take forward.

These insights—realizing intentional self-improvement, gaining new perspectives, and acquiring wisdom from experiences—illustrate the profound self-awareness and transformation that recovering drug dependents achieve as they reintegrate into their communities. They serve as a testament to the power of recovery, highlighting how intentionality, perspective, and reflection can lead to meaningful change and a brighter future.

The findings of this study confirm the applicability of The Centre for Health Promotion model, particularly its multidimensional approach encompassing the "Being," "Belonging," and "Becoming" dimensions. This model provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing the complexities of recovery from drug dependence and the reintegration process into the community. The results highlight how mental and physical health, social functioning, role performance, and overall well-being are interconnected factors that shape an individual's quality of life during recovery.

The "Being" dimension, which encompasses physical, psychological, and spiritual well-being, was reflected in the participants' emphasis on maintaining health-conscious lifestyles, emotional resilience, and spirituality as vital components of their recovery journey. The "Belonging" dimension, which focuses on social relationships, community engagement, and environmental stability, emerged as a significant factor, with participants identifying social support and acceptance as critical to overcoming stigma and navigating reintegration challenges. Lastly, the "Becoming" dimension, centered on personal growth, practical daily activities, and leisure, was evident in the participants' intentional efforts to pursue self-improvement, adopt new life perspectives, and establish meaningful life roles.

By validating the multidimensional approach of the model, this study underscores the importance of addressing a broad spectrum of factors—ranging from individual mental and physical health to the social and environmental conditions that enable sustainable recovery. The results provide a foundation for designing more holistic, person-centered interventions that promote successful reintegration and improve the quality of life for recovering individuals.

Conclusion

This study affirms that the journey of recovering drug dependents and their reintegration into the community is shaped by multiple dimensions of well-being, as highlighted in the Centre for Health Promotion model's framework of Being, Belonging, and Becoming. The findings reveal that while individuals experience challenges in mental and physical health, social functioning, role performance, and general well-being, they also demonstrate resilience when supported by meaningful connections and opportunities for growth. The discussion underscores that reintegration is not merely a personal process but a communal one, where the presence of acceptance, understanding, and shared humanity plays a vital role in fostering healing.

The implications of this study suggest that recovery must extend beyond the individual, requiring the active involvement of families, communities, and institutions in cultivating supportive environments.

Recommendations point toward strengthening community-based programs, enhancing psychosocial interventions, and fostering inclusive spaces where Kapwa, or shared identity and interconnectedness, is lived out in practice.

Ultimately, the conclusion of this study is that rehabilitation and reintegration succeed most meaningfully when grounded in both personal resilience and collective compassion. By embracing the communal spirit, society can create healing spaces that not only restore recovering individuals but also nurture a more compassionate and cohesive community.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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